

Interdisciplinary Assemblages in Digital Humanities Beyond STEM Borrowing: Ethnography in Research Software Engineering and Data Science

Mollenhauer, Sabina

sabina.mollenhauer@uni-vechta.de
 Universität Vechta, Deutschland
 ORCID: 0009-0007-4468-6787

Digital Humanities Between Disciplines

As a field of study with “amorphous” boundaries (Suissa et al. 2022, 268), the digital humanities (DH) encompass computational approaches to address research questions across all fields included in the humanities (ibid.). More specifically, when discussing the skills necessary to practice DH in Germany, web development and digital data processing are emphasized (Sahle 2013, 15). Hence, there is a tendency to consider DH a field that seeks to adopt concepts and methods from data science and software engineering to address research questions within the humanities, thereby developing a data and software engineering practice informed by STEM (science, technology, engineering, and mathematics). In Germany cultural anthropology and more specifically ethnography, remains largely underrepresented in DH. Situated between computational social science (CSS) and DH, though closer to the latter (Franken 2022, 102), its relevance to reversing this unbalanced view of the humanities learning from STEM remains unrecognized. In fact, certain methodologies, research areas, and data practices of ethnography already have a long history of influence on software engineering, particularly user-centered software engineering. This merits renewed attention with a focus on research practices relevant to the emerging subdomain of software engineering: research software engineering (RSE). With regard to digital data processing in DH, applied data science within STEM is undergoing increased academic institutionalization through the creation of data science curricula and course programs. Similarly to software engineering, data science benefits from ethnographic

foundations on research questions attributed to humanities research. As research and curricula in these areas progresses, DH must provide a space to incorporate cultural anthropology in its discourse. Considerations on aspects of ethnography relevant in RSE and data science not only reverse the often-assumed unidirectional flow of knowledge from STEM to the humanities but also illustrate that through a greater emphasis of ethnography in DH, DH can become active in now emerging RSE and data science curricula and practices. After all, technology is embedded in use, and data are always situated within human contexts.

Ethnography and the Foundations of Software Engineering

A central foundation of software engineering is the concept of software requirements (Kotonya and Sommerville 1998). Requirements are typically formulated at the beginning of the engineering process (ibid., 32) and are continuously revisited and refined depending on the development process (Robey et al. 2001, 61). This iterative approach is grounded in a view of technology as tooling embedded in a particular context, designed to solve a problem or support a process that may or may not already include digital tools—a “parts-and-assemblies concept” (Neighbors 1980, 7). A similar understanding of the human-technology relationship is found in science and technology studies (STS), which intersects between ethnography and social science research and where the notion of a “socio-technical assemblage” is central (Vepřek 2024, 15). Within STS, ethnographic methodologies are used to explore such assemblages and their contexts. As research progresses, temporary boundaries defining the research field are drawn by the researcher. Likewise, in software engineering, the determination of a software use context may involve a “domain analysis” (Neighbors 1980, 1) to understand the interactive socio-technical system.

In his approach of using ethnographic methodologies within agile software development, Nandra Surendra develops the ethnography-based Strip Resolution Process (SRP) to design and develop a web application that supports the work flow and decision-making within a financial company. Therein he describes how his process is informed by agile systems development practice together with ethnographic research practice in information systems (2008: 56) and serves the specific purpose of generating user requirements (2008: 60). Similarly, Paay et al. “used a multidisciplinary approach to engineering socially oriented software systems” (2009: 438) to design online software that supports intergenerational play, i.e. between grandparents and children (2009: 443). Both examples are user-centered, as they focus on user requirements and both are based on ethnographic concepts and methods.

Requirements Engineering and Ethnography in Practice

In industrial contexts, domains may be determined and fixated more easily, such as software developed within a company for a specific group of users. In contrast, research software is often intended to be open-source (Struck et al. 2020) and designed to be findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable by a broad range of users and co-developers (Lamprecht et al. 2020). Ideally, this results in a domain space that spans multiple disciplines and practices and is thus more difficult to define. At the same time, RSE is embedded within research processes of different disciplines, presenting opportunities for interdisciplinary collaboration with ethnography. Ethnography has a longstanding tradition of conceptual work and methodological innovation that can support requirements analysis in such complex domain systems. Multi-sited ethnography (Marcus 1995), alongside user-centered collaborative methodologies such as walk-throughs (Light et al. 2018; Amelang 2023) and contextual inquiry (Beyer and Holtzblatt 1995; Bednar and Welch 2009), can be employed to examine existing software to refine requirements and identify mismatches between non-digital practices and digital workflows. Such approaches support the sustainable reuse of research software.

Outside academia in applied software engineering, ethnographic approaches like contextual inquiry (Raven and Flanders 1996) and user-centric requirement, contextualized analysis (Kleemann et al 2022, 10) as well as ethnographic co-design practices (Hodgson et al 2024, 51:4) are crucial when software is intended to integrate into pre-existing, often non-digital practices. However, ethnographic methods are rarely present in RSE. The training of software engineers in industry typically follows well-established curricula. By contrast, 71% of research software engineers are self-taught (Damerow et al. 2025), although dedicated curricula are currently under development (Anzt et al. 2021, 6). Thus, while requirements elicitation is a foundational practice in software engineering, in RSE, development is often driven by highly specific use cases tied to individual research questions (Combemale et al. 2023, 1081). This can result in software that is not easily transferable or reusable, and thus less sustainable. Ethnographic foundations present in SE are lacking in RSE. And through the lack of ethnographic representation in DH, there is no reflective space to develop these foundations further and integrate them into the budding field of RSE, where DH is also underrepresented.

User-Centric Research Software Development

The interdisciplinary methodologies of software engineering provide a valuable basis for the further development of RSE as a systematic, transparent, and research-focused field. However, at events such as de-RSE 2025¹, vignettes from my field notes depict the seemingly scarce presence of

humanities researchers, as highlighted in the discussion following Judith Hartstein’s presentation on “mundane” software, now included in the HiRSE Seminar Series (Hartstein 2025):

Own field notes, 25.02.2025:

[...] The de-RSE Welcome is packed with hundreds of researchers. The speaker talks about the conference being part of the SE conference for more exchange with “real” software engineers. To illustrate this, he asks how many people have a background only in some other field and nearly everybody raises their hand. Then he asks how many people have a background only in SE, and about a dozen raise their hands. Finally, he asks how many people have an academic background in both. About four hands go up. But I’m afraid to raise mine. I feel like all the people I’ve met, all the posters I’ve seen have been in physics and chemistry, and I really do not want to draw attention to myself. [...]

Own field notes, 27.02.2025:

[...] We’ve talked about how important we think user research from our perspectives is for RSE. Judith is worried that no one will understand what she’s talking about. [...] When she’s finished, the audience claps a lot. There’s many questions about the concept of mundane software. They find this obviously intriguing. [...] But there’s a question at the end of the discussion that stirs it in another direction. Someone thanks Judith profusely for providing all this insight. Then they ask what could be done to have more entries like hers at de-RSE events. She eloquently explains that humanities and social science researchers don’t feel addressed by the way that calls are formulated. There are additional responses to this. There seems to be a general agreement that things must change. [...]

The concept of mundane technology was developed in STS, where these phenomena were already explored in 2003 as part of stable, inconspicuous techno-social structures (Michael 2003; Nemer 2024, 75). Hartstein’s analysis of mundane software use sheds light on techno-social practices across research disciplines. Yet the absence of ethnographic researchers at events on actual computational research practice points to a broader gap in the development of research software. Hartstein’s analysis, and the audience’s receptive response, underscore a key misconception: researchers in the humanities are often critiqued for their non-digital practices, yet these very practices may offer a valuable foundation for user-centered research software development. Rather than producing highly specific, one-off software tools developed by predominantly self-taught practitioners, integrating insights from humanities-based research practices into requirements engineering can support the creation of software that is more broadly usable and sustainable. This approach may foster a larger and more inclusive user base and facilitate technological innovation (Catarci et al. 2020, 2). And yet, where is the space within humanities for ethnographers with theoretical and me-

thodological foundations that focus on digital technologies in particular? If DH aspires to grow beyond computational tool use and instead actively shape RSE and its ethnographic research foundations, it must provide this space.

Rethinking Data Science Through Humanities Perspectives

As noted in the introduction, ethnography within DH also provides a relevant foundation for data science. Although data science is often described as an amalgamation of disciplines such as statistics, data mining, databases, and distributed systems (van der Aalst 2016, 3), computing scientist Longbing Cao traces the origins of the term to its first use in 1974, where it was conceived as the processing of established data sets, with the interpretation of data left to other fields (Cao 2017, 4). Cao now favors terms such as “data mining and knowledge discovery” or “data analytics,” emphasizing their current alignment with business-oriented applications, though he also includes behavioral and social analytics (*ibid.*, 5). The interpretative dimension of domain-specific data science, particularly when applied in the humanities, depends significantly on approaches rooted in cultural anthropology. The inherently interpretive stance of the humanities, which views data as socially and culturally embedded, has already been proposed as a key component in the design of emerging data science curricula, including in business and economics contexts (McGillivray et al. 2020; Blevins 2025).

While in the UK, critical data studies have been part of MSc Data Science since 2015 (Bates et al 2020), this approach specifically addresses a “FATE/CDS oriented data science community” (*ibid.*, 425) that references a community with an existing awareness of fairness, accountability, transparency, ethics as well as critical data studies. Gebru and Denton (2024) in addressing the potential harm of machine learning with a focus on computer vision, refer to Barocas et al work “Fairness and Machine Learning” (Barocas et al 2023). Though Barocas et al’s is a work also associated with FATE, Gebru and Denton push towards taking these practices out of a specific context, and elaborate on them beyond “fairness and bias” (Gebru and Denton 2024, 219) by including grounding through contextualization, researcher reflexivity, and participatory approaches. Thus, they not only urge the need to take critical data science approaches beyond existing communities into data science research overall, but also include the methodologies of ethnography in addition to critical data studies. Regarding contextualization, they adopt the perspective of sociotechnical systems, whereby they reference collaborative works that include researchers from science and technology studies (*ibid.*, 276). Though they cite recent works from within data science on reflexive data practices (*ibid.*, 267-273), this is traditionally rooted in philosophically informed social science research (Eberle 1984). Finally, they advocate community-collaborative approaches that are increasingly par-

ticipatory (Gebru and Denton 2024, 280-284) where they reference interdisciplinary researchers from fields including qualitative human-computer interaction, psychology, and pedagogy reminiscent of collaborative approaches in ethnography (Amelang and Beck 2010, 159; Lassiter 2005). Notably, all their references are created in industry contexts.

The only recently created curriculum Data Advocacy for All, which is incorporated in data science courses across disciplines at the University of Colorado, focuses on critical thinking within data science research through a rhetorical approach as it is “both a critical and constructive framework. As a critical lens, rhetorical data studies investigates the links between data, communication, and power in order to better understand how data-driven stories and arguments generate knowledge, garner public attention, and, among other actions, mediate socio-cultural change” (Gries 2024, 4). The curriculum includes critical concepts such as data ethnography, qualitative research foundations, and thick data vs. big data that are relevant in interpreting and processing data within data science².

These examples outside of the German DH context, are reminiscent of existing traditions in critical data (Kitchin and Lauriault 2014) and archival (Gitelman 2013) studies. At the same time, recent contributions on critical data within German DH (Junginger 2025; Gengnagel et al 2025; Dang 2025) should be complemented through ethnographic data contextualization (Franken et al. 2025) and existing participatory ethnographic data practices, to constitute an important foundation with great potential beyond the field of German DH into the wider interdisciplinary space of data science in the German research community. Additional foundations have been laid internationally by researchers such as philosopher of science Sabina Leonelli and STS researcher Anne Beaulieu (Beaulieu and Leonelli 2021). Through its incorporation of these theoretical and research foundations from humanities in general and ethnography in particular, DH in Germany can actively shape an ethical ethnographic data science practice.

Bridging the Gap: Ethnography as an Interdisciplinary Connector

Software engineering and data science have always been interdisciplinary by nature. Both encompass a wide range of research foundations not exhaustively addressed here, such as formal modeling, documentation, and development practices. In addition, critical data science relies on more than qualitative research, as it includes aspects such as data minimization (Konečný et al 2016) or assessing environmental impact (Strubell et al 2019). Nonetheless, humanities disciplines have much to contribute to subfields of computer science. Ethnography, with its iterative methodologies and capacity to develop flexible and extensible data sets and research contexts (Franken 2022, 102), exemplifies the often-overlooked potential of truly interdisciplinary collaboration. Similarly, the multidisciplinary nature of data sci-

ence depends upon active inclusion of existing theoretical and methodological foundations of ethnography. Moving beyond dichotomous frameworks that juxtapose STEM and the humanities is essential, as such binaries contribute to the persistent undervaluation of the latter (Olmos-Peñuela 2015).

Such interdisciplinary work requires understanding each other despite different "data ideologies" (Poirier 2020 2013), whereas different disciplines may have different data practices, which require practicing openness "for still-to-be imagined purposes, with yet-to-be-named collaborators" (Poirier 2020, 226). Oftentimes, however a heightened tolerance of ambiguity among different disciplinary languages can be addressed through translatory practices (Halahew 2012: 33, Paay 2009: 438). Both aspects suggest a need for open negotiation and respect for different disciplinary practices, neither of which should be underestimated when establishing a new common, interdisciplinary practice.

Finally, the integration of ethnographic methodologies into RSE and data science offers a robust framework for user-centered, sustainable, and interdisciplinary technological development and contextualized data science research. Revisiting the foundational contributions of ethnography in the humanities not only diversifies the epistemological bases of software and data practices but also promotes a more inclusive and reflective approach to software in research and research in software development. Bridging these domains systematically can foster richer, more durable collaborations and innovation across disciplinary boundaries. If we consider DH as a "trading zone" (Galison 1999, 137–160) among humanities disciplines with a focus on digital practices, ethnography is well positioned to serve as a conceptual and methodological bridge within DH to RSE and data science, if – that is – DH in Germany provides a space to reflect and develop ethnographic research on computational tools and resources in the same way as DH makes use of them. The need and potential to contribute to the research-based data science and RSE in Germany can only be addressed from within DH.

Footnotes

1. 5th conference for Research Software Engineering Germany, <https://events.hifis.net/event/2050/>, accessed 23 July 2025.

2. Toolkit | Data Advocacy for All, <https://da4all.github.io/toolkit/>, accessed 29 July 2025.

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